

Enriching contact information through Fiber Bragg Gratings-based exteroception in soft bending actuators

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Abstract—Tactile sensing is of utmost importance for accomplishing fine manipulation tasks and extracting crucial physical features in soft grippers. A contact force estimation and localization approach that relies on sensing modality based on Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) transducers and artificial intelligence models are proposed for pneumatically driven soft fingers. The small packaged sensor unit enables modular design, ease of assembly, and high repeatability with negligible effects on the mechanical performance of the soft finger. The proposed neural networks process the output of the sensing modality and mitigate errors from material nonlinearity, fabrication, and assembly of soft fingers. This, in turn, enhances the accuracy and transferability of force and position estimations, leading to proper metrological indicators. These results provide a step forward in the development of smart soft grippers enabling them to attain "transparent" exteroception and empowering them with skillful capabilities to acquire precise tactile information for safe and delicate manipulation ranging from agricultural to biomedical fields.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, soft robots have been gradually introduced in biomedical applications, extreme environment exploration, robotic manipulation, and grasping to operate delicate and fragile objects [1], due to the merits of excellent compliance and environmental adaptability [2]. However, these merits also bring considerable challenges to the precise control [3]. Indeed, perception is crucial for autonomous and intelligent soft robots [4] to achieve accurate closed-loop motion control and safe interaction with the environment in complex tasks. In particular, tactile information is essential for grasping skilled tasks (e.g., dexterous manipulations, grasping unknown objects, etc.). Among different physical information, force sensing is pivotal for soft grippers, which have a bearing on the interaction with the surroundings. The weight of the grasped object and the information about the stress status of the soft gripper can be directly derived from the perception of the contact force including its magnitude, direction, and distribution [4] [5]. In particular, soft grippers provided with embedded tactile sensors could grasp fragile objects without causing damage, since effective and reliable force feedback control strategies could be easily implemented. However, the direct attachment of traditional commercial sensors on

the robot surface would affect the motion of the soft robot itself. These transducers are typically electronic products that present high stiffness, large volume, or poor stretchability, thus impacting their integrability in soft robotic systems. In order to address these challenges, several approaches have been explored so far for providing soft robots with tactile sensing. Among the flexible and stretchable solutions, capacitive [6], piezoresistive [7], piezoelectric [8], triboelectric [9], and magnetic [10], sensing approaches have been proposed in literature. Nonetheless, stretchable electronic sensors commonly exhibit nonlinearity and hysteresis issues and an overall quality that strongly depends on the fabrication process, ending up with nonuniform structures. These drawbacks finally result in poor measurement accuracy and frequency, a tedious calibration procedure, and a lack of transferability [5]. In this scenario, stable and robust sensors would be desirable. A possibility is represented by Fiber Bragg Gratings (FBGs), which are recently attracting significant research attention due to their high mechanical sensitivity, flexibility, safety, multiplexing, immunity to electromagnetic interference, and distributed sensing capabilities [11]. In particular, FBGs have been widely used in force and curvature sensing of rigid robotic fingers [12], [13], [14] and have been introduced for soft robotic proprioception [15] [16], but there are still a few studies on FBG-based tactile sensing approaches for soft grippers. As an example, in [17], the authors proposed an object shape and roughness recognition method for a soft robotic finger. However, there are still limited applications of FBGs in soft robotics, and their outstanding sensing capabilities have not been deeply explored in this field yet. In addition, smart sensing systems that can reliably identify tactile interactions with the surroundings could be developed by implementing artificial intelligence algorithms, as proposed in [18] [19]. In this framework, this work presents a pneumatically driven soft finger with FBG-mediated exteroceptive capabilities, enabled through artificial neural networks (ANN). An array of FBG sensors has been embedded in the soft actuator to measure touch-related deformations while preserving its bending behavior. Two ANNs have been trained for force prediction and localization of tactile events applied over the finger pad, starting from the information sensed by the FBGs. The main achievement of this study is the development of a new soft FBG-based sensing finger able to accurately infer tactile events by means of artificial intelligence. The presented proof of concept paves the way to more sophisticated soft robotic

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solutions for skillful object manipulation, where interaction force and configuration can be modulated by closed-loop control strategies of smart grippers. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In section II, we provide a brief description of the FBG working principle and its integration into a pneumatic soft finger. We introduce the experimental setup used for controlled indentation tests and the ANN models implemented for contact force and location predictions. In section III, we present and discuss the ANN results. Finally, in section IV, we draw our conclusions on the work.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Working principle and fabrication of the FBG sensing system

FBGs are microstructures with a typical length between 1 and 15 mm inscribed in the core of a single-mode optical fiber [20]. They consist of periodic modulations of the refractive index of the core that determine resonant interference patterns locally distributed along the fiber wire. Hence, when a broadband spectrum light source is injected into the optical fiber, typically through an optical interrogator, the FBG unit functions as a narrow-band filter. Consequently, a portion of the spectrum is transmitted and propagates along the fiber, while the remaining narrow portion is back-reflected to the input and read by the optical interrogator. The reflected signal is a spectral peak centered around the Bragg wavelength (λ_B), which is defined as in Equation (1):

$$\lambda_B = 2n_{eff}\Lambda_B \quad (1)$$

where, n_{eff} is the effective refraction index of the fiber core and Λ_B is the grating period. FBGs exhibit an outstanding sensitivity to mechanical deformations that lead to variations of λ_B [21]. One of the primary benefits of this technology is wavelength multiplexing, i.e., the possibility to distinguish numerous gratings inscribed within a single optical fiber, with major advantages on wiring and cable routing issues that usually affect electronic-based sensing systems. To benefit from this feature and prevent any overlap of multiple output peaks, each sensor must have physical characteristics guaranteeing that its back-reflected signal is centered around a specific wavelength that is different from the others. In this work, five 3 mm-long FBG sensors (central wavelengths: FBG1-1534.71 nm, FBG2-1544.67 nm, FBG3-1554.62 nm, FBG4-1564.33 nm, FBG5-1574.60 nm) have been inscribed in a low-bending-loss polyimide-coated single-mode fiber using a femtolaser machine (Newport femtoFBG). Each sensor has been placed at 10 mm from the neighbors (center-to-center distance) on a straight path to entirely cover the soft finger pad (Fig. 1d).

B. Fabrication of the sensorized soft finger

The tapered Pneu-net configuration with a series of chambers connected by channels was adopted to design the soft finger with all its relevant dimensions reported in [?]. The fabrication of the soft pneumatic finger consisted of a multi-step open molding procedure. The molds were designed

FIG. 1: Experimental setup for sensorized soft finger indentations. It comprised (a) a mechatronic platform made up of linear motorized stages (X, Y, and Z axes) to perform automatic indentations of the finger; air compressor and proportional valve for finger actuation; optical interrogator for FBGs readout; (b) indenter attached to a load cell for force measurements; (c) soft finger embedding 5 FBGs transducers in its pad middle plane.

using SolidWorks and 3D-printed using a ProJet MJP 3600 from 3D Systems. The two reagents of the Dragon Skin 30A (Smooth-On, USA) silicone rubber were mixed in equal parts, degassed in a vacuum oven, and poured into the molds for the upper and bottom layers. In particular, sensorized bottom layer was carried out in two steps. First fabricating a half-height bottom layer with an engraving for the optical fiber. The optical fiber was integrated with the longitudinal axis and laterally centered in the middle of the bottom layer through silicone adhesive (SilPoxy, Smooth-On, USA) as shown in Fig. 1c. Then uncured silicone was poured over to encapsulate the optical fiber and create a sealed environment for the sensor. Finally, after the demoulding process, the upper and sensorized bottom parts were joined using a small quantity of uncured silicone and inserting the pipe for the air.

C. Experimental setup and protocol for controlled indentation tests

To collect FBG sensor data and ultimately correlate them with force and location measurements, a mechatronic platform was built to perform automatic indentations throughout the bottom layer of the soft finger surface. The main body of the setup consisted of three motorized linear stages (horizontal stages: 8MTF102LS05; vertical stage: 8MVT120-25-4247; STANDA, Vilnius, Lithuania) that moved the finger along the three Cartesian axes (XYZ in 1). The motion along XY and Z was performed with a 2.5 μm and 5 μm step resolution, respectively. An aluminum cylindrical probe of 10 mm diameter was used to indent the finger. The indenter was mechanically attached to a load cell (Nano

FIG. 2: Experimental indentation procedure and data acquisition. (a) Workflow of the experimental protocol. (b) Collected raw data showing the wavelength variation of the five FBG sensors and the corresponding force magnitude overtime at 200 mbar.

43; ATI Industrial Automation, Apex, NC), to collect data about the force arising from the contact between the finger and the probe. The load cell was secured to an external aluminum frame (not represented for the sake of clarity) that supported the entire platform and guaranteed stability to the structure. The finger was fixed to the uppermost linear stage through a 3D printed holder (blue case in 1a,b) screwed in a metallic plate to provide it with steadiness during the inflation. The air input was controlled by a proportional pressure regulator (VPPE-3-1-1/8-6-010-E1, Festo AG & Co, Germany) directly connected to an air compressor (SIL-AIR 50 D, Werther International S.p.A., Italy). An optical interrogator (FBG-Scan 904, FBGS International NV, Belgium) was used to read data from the five FBG transducers, namely the reflected wavelengths of the different gratings over time. All the components of the setup were controlled at a 100 Hz sampling rate through a custom LabVIEW routine (National Instruments Corp., Austin, TX) using a PC and a graphical user interface. The software ensured the automated execution of the protocol and the synchronized collection of the force and the FBG readings and the pressure and platform position inputs. The protocol consisted of a continuous set of automatic indentations of the finger in seven different sites along the longitudinal direction of the finger at eight input

pressures, from 100 to 800 mbar with a step of 100 mbar. The reference position was a point located at about 15 mm from the proximal edge of the finger in between the first two sensors (FBG1 and FBG2, Fig. 1b). At the beginning of each trial, the linear stages reached this position, where the indenter was detached from the finger (2a first step). This condition was essential to collect baseline values of both the FBG and the force sensors, the latter loaded with only the weight of the indenting tool. Then, the vertical stage moved upward to make the finger pad come in contact with the metallic instrument (Fig. 2a second step). Once touched, the finger was inflated at P_i pressure for 5 s and then deflated. The next position, 5 mm apart along the finger longitudinal axis (Y), was then reached after 5 s of pause. This transition was performed by keeping the soft actuator surface and the indenter tip in touch. The inflation-deflation cycle was hence repeated following the above-mentioned procedure. The trial finished when the stages had moved the finger along the Y axis up to its tip (Fig. 2a third step) and it had been pressurized. Thereafter, the linear motors flew back to the initial position to start a new trial with a changed target pressure value. Considering such a procedure, each experimental session consisted of 56 indentations (7 sites per trial and 8 pressures) that was repeated 5 times, hence reaching 280 measurements.

D. Contact force and location prediction

The relevant signals were collected and saved in dedicated text files during the indentation protocol. Specifically, three-component force, FBG sensors, pressure, and position 10 s (5 s air inflation and 5 s air deflation) time series were recorded and pre-processed to remove potential outlier values. In addition, the load cell and the FBG outputs were unbiased by removing the initial position baseline from the signals of each trial (Fig. 2b). Force magnitude sequences were then extracted from the three-component force raw data (Fig. 2b) to be further predicted by a neural network. Specifically, force and FBG data points belonging to all the indentations were shuffled and split into training (70% of the dataset, i.e., 197141 values), validation (15% of the dataset, i.e., 42245 values), and test (15% of the dataset, i.e., 42245 values) sets. A shallow neural network including one dense layer with 20 hidden neurons (Fig. 3a) was trained to estimate the regression model that correlates the input, i.e., the five FBG sensor wavelength variations, with the corresponding target force magnitude. The Levenberg-Marquardt back-propagation algorithm was implemented to minimize a Mean Square Error (MSE) loss function and an early stopping strategy with six steps of diverging validation loss was considered. Data fitting and target-output correlation parameters were extrapolated to assess the accuracy of the trained model in predicting force magnitude values. To further enhance the exteroceptive features of the soft finger, an approach for localizing touch events was conceived. A neural network with three dense layers, integrating 50, 20, and 20 hidden neurons respectively, was modeled for position classification purposes. Seven classes, i.e., from position 1,

FIG. 3: Neural networks for force prediction and localization of touch events. (a) Force magnitude regression model. Left: neural network block diagram. Right: learning curves. (b) Position classification model. Left: neural network block diagram. Right: learning curves.

on the proximal finger, to position 7, on the fingertip, were the target groups to correlate with the inputs, i.e., the FBG sensor wavelength variations. As for the force regression algorithm, both the input and the target datasets were shuffled and split into the three sub-sets, with the same partition rule. The scaled conjugate gradient back-propagation method was used to minimize the Cross-Entropy (CE) loss function and the same early stopping strategy was adopted. The accuracy performance of the network to recognize the touch event locations was then evaluated through confusion matrices and Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curves. Both the algorithms were implemented in MATLAB (MathWorks, Inc.), by means of built-in functions of the proprietary *ntool*.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

ANN performance results in terms of the best loss values (MSE and CE for the force regression and the position classification models, respectively) at the number of training epochs reached (524 for the force and 4538 for the position networks) are reported in Tab. I. In both cases, the training process stopped when the validation criterion was met i.e. early stopping. The corresponding learning curves for the training, validation, and test processes are represented in Fig. 3 and show that similar and converging accuracy has been reached on the three subsets in both the regression and the classification cases. The achieved performance suggests that the split and randomization of data points across the subsets were effectively performed, promoting good generalization capabilities of the network. Regarding the regression of force magnitudes, 4a represents the distribution of predicted versus target values, ranging between 0 N (when no contact and/or air inflation occurred) and 4 N. The point clouds are reported for each subset and have an around the diagonal (i.e., perfect prediction, dashed grey line) flattened shape. These results

are supported by the computed linear correlation parameters R , which are 0.934, 0.939, and 0.934 for the training, the validation, and the test sets, respectively. In addition, the data fitting curves were extracted as well, and are represented with solid colored lines in Fig. 4a. The linear relationship rules between the target and the output groups are also reported as y-axis labels of each graph of Fig. 4a. Regarding the localization problem, the FBG sensor outputs were utilized to classify the seven touch positions obtained during the experimental sessions. To evaluate the approach, some summary indicators were derived. Specifically, a confusion matrix was computed for each subset (Fig. 4b). At first glance, the consistency between the results across the training, the validation, and the test sets can be noticed, with an overall classification accuracy of 75.6%, 75.3%, and 75.6%, respectively. These similarities, also confirmed by the ROC curves (Fig. 4b), along with the standard indicators of the algorithm performance, suggest again that the network is likely to fairly generalize on new data. A thorough examination of the outcomes presented in Fig. 4b provides information about the single-position classification accuracy. In more detail, when the finger was touched on its most proximal region, the embedded sensors encoded much more useful information than in the case of contacts occurring near the fingertip. In this regard, position 1 was correctly recognized in about 90% of the cases (confusion matrices of Fig. 4b) in contrast to the 60% accuracy values obtained for the most distal position 7. This result is also outlined by the corresponding ROC curves, with the position 1 line representing the skillfulness of the classifier in almost perfectly recognizing it. However, all the ROCs pointed towards the top-left corner of the graph, far away from the central random guess diagonal, demonstrating that the model was fairly sensitive and specific in each target condition. The reduction in classifier accuracy

FIG. 4: Outcomes of the neural networks for force (a) and contact (b) inference for training, validation, and test subsets. Results (a) of the force regression model in terms of fitting curves and correlation parameters and (b) of the contact position classification in terms of confusion matrices and ROC curves.

observed when transitioning from the base to the tip of the finger can likely be attributed to the indentation protocol utilized. In this procedure, the linear stages advanced from one position to the next without detaching the indenting tool from the finger pad. This caused slight residual strains in both the soft structure and the fiber, changing the initial conditions of further indentations. In addition, up to half the length of the indentation path, the finger was almost entirely free to bend when pressurized. When indenting the tip, instead, its movement was blocked by the indenter, thus changing the deformation patterns of both the silicone structure and the sensors. In light of these considerations, we expect that enhanced performance in localization accuracy might be achieved by adding intermediate conditions, i.e.,

the probe does not touch the finger surface, and allowing free bending movements of the actuator at each indentation. Furthermore, the complexity of the learning model is another aspect to consider. Deeper and larger networks might infer non-linear underlying relationships between the input and the target signals that simple models are usually not able to. In this perspective, the implementation of deep learning approaches and memory-based architectures (e.g., Long Short-Term Memory, Temporal Convolutional Networks, etc.) that, for instance, store the relevant temporal information about the deformation behavior of both the silicone substrate and the optical fiber, could even more accurate outcomes. Further efforts will also deal with a driven-by-desired performance design of new paths of the embedded fiber to enhance its

	Force Regression (MSE)	Position Classification (CE)
<i>Training</i>	0.0859	0.0875
<i>Validation</i>	0.0838	0.883
<i>Test</i>	0.0869	0.876

TABLE I: Loss performance of the force regression and position classification models.

robustness and the inference results.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

As robotic technology progresses, the research and applications of smart soft grippers to complex and challenging scenarios, notably those underscored by requirements of safety and compliance, have attracted increasing attention. The aid of intelligent tactile sensing allows the extraction of vital physical characteristics unlocking more sophisticated grasping abilities. In this paper, we introduced a distributed exteroceptive sensing method for soft-bending actuators leveraging the outstanding capabilities of Fiber Bragg Gratings (FBG). Simple artificial neural network-based models facilitate the predictions of contact force and locations through the processing of sensor output data. In particular, the sensing system generates negligible interference with the bending performances, demonstrating a modular sensory design for empowering soft fingers with refined skills and enabling enhanced controllability. This work establishes the proof of concept for an innovative exteroceptive sensing approach that holds promise for enriching contact information with delicate objects in soft robotic systems. These promising results obtained with simplified neural network-based models encourage further investigation aimed at refining force and location predictions to facilitate the implementation of a real-time closed-loop control strategy. This contributes to addressing the growing demand for automation across a broad range of applications e.g. agri-food, and biomedical fields, where smart soft grippers provided with the sense of touch can acquire tactile information accurately, cope with uncertainty, and handle fragile objects safely.

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